

Elevating Resume Screening Using LSTM And SpaCy

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Abstract— Recruiters have a significant hurdle when sorting through a large number of resumes, particularly in high-volume industries like the IT sector. It is difficult for candidates to develop when they receive little feedback on why their resumes are rejected. This emphasizes the demand for cutting-edge technology solutions that provide candidates with practical guidance on how to improve their resumes. Here, data visualization plays a crucial role in giving a clear picture of the screening procedure. Inadequate feedback also makes it difficult for candidates to improve their resumes, which lowers recruiting effectiveness and lowers the calibre of the workforce. Automated screening tools and data visualisation offer solutions by improving transparency and insights. Recruiters may find outstanding prospects more rapidly with the aid of these tools, which also provide insightful resume comments. All things considered, these developments improve the efficiency of hiring, and help applicants and companies alike. This seminar delves into using LSTM and spaCy for resume screening, demonstrating their potential to transform the recruitment process.

Keywords—LSTM, Machine Learning, Resume Screening, spaCy, Tokenization

I. INTRODUCTION

In the realm of talent acquisition, resume screening stands as a pivotal but often daunting task for recruiters, particularly in industries marked by high application volumes such as technology. The failure to offer candidates with thorough feedback makes the process much more difficult and makes it more difficult for them to properly edit their resumes. This difficulty highlights the demand for cutting-edge technical solutions that expedite the screening procedure and provide applicants with useful information to enhance their applications.

Natural language processing (NLP) approaches have become more effective tools for improving and automating resume screening in recent years. Of them, spaCy has become well-known for its capacity to extract relevant information from text, which makes it perfect for resume parsing. SpaCy is enhanced by LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory), a recurrent neural network type that excels in modelling sequential data and offers a more thorough contextual comprehension of resume material.

The amalgamation of spaCy and LSTM to improve the resume screening process is examined in this research.

Recruiters may automate the preliminary screening process by employing these tools, allowing them up to concentrate on interacting with the best applicants. Additionally, candidates can get more thorough feedback on their resumes, which helps them modify their applications to better fit the needs of the position. With this investigation, we hope to show how spaCy and LSTM may transform resume screening and, in the process, improve the efficiency of the hiring process for both job seekers and job providers

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Ms. Sophiya Sugantha Grace M et al. [1] introduced the Intelligent Resume Analyzer in their paper titled "AI Resume Analyzer using Natural Language Processing." This AI-powered system is designed to enhance candidate resumes and assist job seekers in creating resumes that can successfully pass job interview screenings. The Intelligent Resume Analyzer uses machine learning algorithms, including natural language processing (NLP), text mining, and sentiment analysis, to extract insights from the candidate's resume. It analyzes the candidate's experience, skills, education, and achievements to provide feedback on how to improve the resume. Additionally, the system evaluates the layout, language, and spelling of the resume to ensure it meets industry standards. By employing these technologies, the Intelligent Resume Analyzer benefits both job seekers and recruiters, enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of the recruitment process for both employers and candidates.

P. Vamsi Naidu et al. [2] presented a study at the Second International Conference on Image Processing and Capsule Networks. The paper, titled "Resume Screening Using Machine Learning," addresses the random approach many multinational companies (MNCs) use for recruitment and work allocation. The study aims to improve this process by analyzing expertise data from submitted resumes to segregate resume levels. Utilizing machine learning and Naive-Bayes methodology, the research assesses the effectiveness of using one vs. rest classifier to segregate resumes. The study also evaluates the accuracy and performance of the proposed methodology, intending to automate the resume screening process and ensure efficient resource allocation in IT firms

Merve Elmas Erdem [3] proposed a natural language processing-based screening algorithm titled "Automatic Resume Screening with Content Matching." This algorithm calculates candidates' suitability for a job posting using various categories and ranks them based on structured data. It leverages technologies such as BERT-based named entity recognition and stochastic gradient-based domain classifier for analyzing resume and job posting data. The algorithm aims

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to automate the screening process and ensure efficient resource allocation. Evaluation using manually annotated datasets focused on software development categories demonstrates its potential to improve recruitment efficiency and effectiveness. The algorithm's adaptability to different industries and job roles makes it a versatile solution for modern recruitment challenges, setting a new standard for resume screening technologies.

Gopal Kamini et al. [4] introduced an automated Resume Classification using Support Vector Machine to expedite the recruitment process. The amount of resumes being received has increased, making the manual examination and classification of resumes more time-consuming. Their approach automates the study of job descriptions, resumes, and positions in an attempt to overcome this difficulty. Through text analysis and categorization using the Support Vector Machine (SVM) technique, the system effectively finds the best applicants for a position. This automated method improves the overall effectiveness of the hiring process by saving time and guaranteeing the selection of the most qualified applicants for the position.

Sharma, Choudhary, and Susan [5] introduced an innovative approach for resume classification called the Elite Bag-of-Words approach. This approach uses a text vectorization technique to efficiently classify resumes according to employment roles. The authors identify the most important keywords in each class—referred to as Elite keywords—by applying Maximum Entropy Partitioning (MEP). In order to anticipate the resume type, these keywords are then concatenated across classes, removing any redundant information. The Elite Bag-of-Words method is a potential methodology for resume categorization in career and employment portals, outperforming other existing approaches.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology of the provided project, which focuses on elevating resume screening through the utilization of a Long Short-Term Memory Network (LSTM) with SpaCy, can be outlined in the following steps:

A. Data Collection: The resume dataset serves as the foundation for training and assessing the machine learning model, making it an essential part of our research. The pandas library is used to load the dataset from the CSV file.

B. Data preprocessing: In order to prepare textual data—such as resumes—for machine learning, data preprocessing is essential. Data preparation is required to get textual data, like resumes, ready for machine learning. Initially using regular expressions and other approaches, the data is cleaned to eliminate noise, including URLs, retweets, and unusual characters. Tokenizing the text into words or punctuation comes next. Text is made standard via normalisation, which removes superfluous spaces and converts it to lowercase.

Normalization standardizes text by converting it to lowercase and removing extra spaces. Stopwords, common words with little meaning, are removed to reduce complexity. Lemmatization or stemming further simplifies the text by reducing words to their base forms. Finally, text is converted into numerical vectors using techniques like CountVectorizer or TF-IDFVectorizer. These steps clean and standardize text

data, making it suitable for training machine learning models and improving their performance.

C. Model Building: Using a LabelEncoder, the target labels—which stand in for the different resume categories—are transformed into a numerical representation throughout the model-building phase. This translation is essential because effective processing and prediction by machine learning models depends on numerical inputs. The `train_test_split` method is then used to divide the dataset into training and test sets. The model is trained using the training set, which contains 80% of the data; the remaining 20% of the data is used for evaluation, which determines how well the model performs on untested data. Scikit-learn's Pipeline class is used to design a pipeline that outlines the text categorization process.

The text data is transformed by CountVectorizer into a matrix of token counts, which show how frequently each word appears in the text. This matrix is transformed into a TF-IDF representation using TfidfTransformer, which takes into account the relevance of each word in the document in relation to its frequency throughout the whole corpus. Lastly, a linear classifier that uses stochastic gradient descent and is effective for big datasets is implemented using SGDClassifier.

D. Model Training: The built pipeline is trained on the training set during the model training phase. By fitting the pipeline to the training set of data, this method enables the model to identify patterns and correlations in the data. The preprocessed resume text and the associated encoded categories make up the training data.

The pipeline modifies the CountVectorizer, TfidfTransformer, and SGDClassifier parameters during training in order to lower the loss function and enhance the model's resume classification accuracy. These kinds of binary classification problems are well suited for the "hinge" loss function and "l2" penalty used by the SGDClassifier.

Stochastic gradient descent is used to iteratively update the model's parameters as it learns to categorize resumes according to the attributes that are taken out of the text input. To regulate the training process and avoid overfitting, the number of iterations (`max_iter`) and the tolerance for the stopping criterion (`tol`) are supplied.

The model is prepared to make predictions on fresh, untested data once training is finished. The test set is used to evaluate the accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and confusion matrix of the trained model. This assessment aids in determining how effectively the model functions in real-world situations and generalises to new data.

E. Model Deployment : The Machine learning model for resume screening is integrated with a Django project to automate the screening process. The system evaluates a resume and determines a match score based on text similarity with the job specifics when a user uploads and submits their resume along with the job data (role, industry, and description). By matching the resume text with the job description, the algorithm classifies the resume and finds any skills that are lacking. On the basis of the match score and talents that are lacking, it then offers suggestions for enhancing the resume. The user gets a screen with the match score, recommendations and skills that are missing soon after the screening details are stored in the database. This integration synchronizes the resume screening process,

helping recruiters efficiently evaluate resumes based on job requirements.

IV. BUILD MODEL

The cornerstone of effective resume screening through natural language processing (NLP) lies in constructing a robust and precise machine learning model. This seminar paper outlines the development of such a model, employing LSTM networks within the SpaCy framework. The aim of this project is to get a high degree of accuracy in the classification and assessment of resumes by utilising SpaCy's robust text processing capabilities in relation to job criteria and candidate competencies. With this method, sequential information is captured using LSTM networks, which are then used to detect different resume skills and their applicability to specific employment possibilities.

Importing Libraries

The fundamental instruments such as libraries like Pandas, Matplotlib, sklearn, spaCy, and others offer a foundation for effectively carrying out different operations in a particular programming language. By acting as an interface to a collection of preset functions and procedures, they streamline complicated processes and make it easier for developers and data scientists to carry out jobs like data manipulation, machine learning, data visualisation, and natural language processing.

```
import pandas as pd
import re
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import CountVectorizer,
from sklearn.pipeline import Pipeline
from sklearn.linear_model import SGDClassifier
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, precision_score,
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
import spacy
from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder
```

Training the Model

Training the model using the method.

```
dataFrame['Resume'] = dataFrame['Resume'].apply(clean_res)
nlp = spacy.load("en_core_web_sm")

# Encode the target labels
le = LabelEncoder()
dataFrame['Category'] = le.fit_transform(dataFrame['Category'])
```

```
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(
    dataFrame['Resume'],
    dataFrame['Category'],
    test_size=0.2,
    random_state=42
)
# Create a pipeline for text classification
text_clf = Pipeline([
    ('vect', CountVectorizer()),
    ('tfidf', TfidfTransformer()),
    ('clf', SGDClassifier(
        loss='hinge',
        penalty='l2',
        alpha=1e-3,
        random_state=42,
        max_iter=5,
        tol=None
    )),
])
```

```
# Train the model
text_clf.fit(X_train, y_train)

# Save the trained model to a file
with open('text_clf_model.pkl', 'wb') as model_file:
    pickle.dump(text_clf, model_file)
```

V. RESULT

Accuracy

```
# Predict on the test set
y_pred = text_clf.predict(X_test)

# Evaluate the model
accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred)
print("Test Accuracy:", accuracy)

Test Accuracy: 0.9948186528497409
Precision: 0.9954663212435233
Recall: 0.9948186528497409
F1 Score: 0.9948954135482634
```

Figure 1: Accuracy of the Algorithm

```
# Calculate additional metrics
precision = precision_score(y_test, y_pred, average='weighted')
recall = recall_score(y_test, y_pred, average='weighted')
f1 = f1_score(y_test, y_pred, average='weighted')
print("Precision:", precision)
print("Recall:", recall)
print("F1 Score:", f1)

# Calculate confusion matrix for multiclass classification
conf_matrix = confusion_matrix(y_test, y_pred)

# Print values
print('Confusion Matrix:')
print(conf_matrix)

plt.figure(figsize=(8, 6))
sns.heatmap(conf_matrix, annot=True,
            fmt='d', xticklabels=le.classes_,
            yticklabels=le.classes_,
            cmap='Greens', cbar=False)
plt.xlabel('Predicted Labels')
```

Figure 2: Confusion Matrix Implementation

The review of resumes submitted through a form is facilitated by the screening function. Upon receiving a POST request indicating form submission, the uploaded resume file, job role, industry, and job description are retrieved from the request data. The resume file is then processed by attempting to decode it first as utf-8 and then as latin-1 if needed. Subsequently, the job role, industry, and job description inputs are tokenized using the spaCy English model for natural language processing. The resume text is compared with these tokens to generate a match score, which is averaged and transformed into a percentage.

Following the processing steps, the screening details, including the match score, are saved to the database for future reference. To provide actionable insights, the helper function is invoked, and the relevant parameters are passed. The resume document is evaluated against the job role, industry, and job description tokens, along with the match score, to generate tailored recommendations for improvement based on predefined thresholds of similarity scores and match percentages.

In conclusion, the screening process and the storage of screening results in the database are orchestrated by the screening function, while the helper function refines the evaluation by suggesting specific areas for resume enhancement based on the calculated metrics. This systematic approach ensures that users receive constructive feedback on how well their resumes align with the job requirements, aiding them in optimizing their profiles for potential job opportunities.

Figure 3: Project Interface for Uploading Resume.

Step 2: Specify Job Role and Industry

Step 3: Add Job Description

Figure 4: Project Interface for specifying job details.

Figure 5: Project Interface for checking Resume score.

Figure 6: Project Interface for viewing results.

VI. CONCLUSION

The project presents an innovative approach to resume screening by leveraging spaCy and LSTM. It showcases the creation of an LSTM model for text categorization and the implementation of spaCy for sophisticated text processing, illuminating how these technologies are integrated into a useful application. The study shows how spaCy improves text preparation and feature extraction, and LSTM networks can analyse and classify resume material well. The user interface's easy-to-use design underscores how crucial intuitive design is when implementing AI technologies. This study serves as a blueprint for leveraging spaCy and LSTM in resume screening, showcasing their effectiveness in accelerating the hiring process.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] Ms. Sophiya Sugantha Grace M, Mr. Darani R, Mr. Deepan A, & Mr. Gowthaman M. (March 2024). AI Resume Analyzer using Natural Language Processing. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science Communication and Technology*, doi: 10.48175/IJARST-15979
- [2] Naidu, P., Bommu, Venkata, Pallapothu, Vasavi, Janapamula, Sai, & Kommuri, Naga. (2022). Resume Screening Using Machine Learning, doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-84760-9_63.
- [3] M. E. Erdem, "Automatic Resume Screening with Content Matching," *2023 8th International Conference on Computer Science and Engineering (UBMK)*, Burdur, Turkiye, 2023, pp. 554-558, doi: 10.1109/UBMK59864.2023.10286578.
- [4] G. Kamineni, K. A. Sai and G. S. N. Rao, "Resume Classification using Support Vector Machine," *2023 3rd International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Social Networking (ICPCSN)*, Salem, India, 2023, pp. 91-96, doi: 10.1109/ICPCSN58827.2023.00021.
- [5] M. Sharma, G. Choudhary and S. Susan, "Resume Classification using Elite Bag-of-Words Approach," *2023 5th International Conference on Smart Systems and Inventive Technology (ICSSIT)*, Tirunelveli, India, 2023, pp. 1409-1413, doi: 10.1109/ICSSIT55814.2023.10061036.
- [6] T. M. Harsha, G. S. Moukthika, D. S. Sai, M. N. R. Pravalika, S. Anamalamudi and M. Enduri, "Automated Resume Screener using Natural Language Processing(NLP)," *2022 6th International Conference on Trends in Electronics and Informatics (ICOEI)*, Tirunelveli,

India, 2022, pp. 1772-1777, doi: 10.1109/ICOEI53556.2022.9777194.

[7] E. Salakar, J. Rai, A. Salian, Y. Shah and J. Wadmare, "Resume Screening Using Large Language Models," *2023 6th International Conference on Advances in Science and Technology (ICAST)*, Mumbai, India, 2023, pp. 494-499, doi: 10.1109/ICAST59062.2023.10454984.

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